

DESIGN AND INITIAL TESTING OF A
THREE-AXIS CURRENT METER
by

Henry Perkins¹, Kim Saunders¹,
Gerald Appell² and Thomas Mero²

- 1) Naval Ocean Research and Development Activity, NSTL Station, MS 39529
- 2) NOAA Test and Evaluation Laboratory, Rockville, MD 20852

ABSTRACT

A prototype of an attended 3-axis acoustic current meter/CTD has been built and has undergone extensive laboratory testing. In addition to a conventional CTD sensor head, the instrument includes transducers for measuring current velocity along three paths, three components of earth magnetic field and three components of acceleration.

Reported here are results of testing the velocity sensors in a tow tank. A noteworthy feature of the instrument design is that the acoustic paths, along which the current velocity is measured, are arranged so that disturbance of the measured flow by supporting struts or by the sensors themselves is greatly reduced. Estimated errors in the velocity measurements are found to be characteristically on the order of a few tenths of a percent at a speed of 40 cm/sec.

1. INTRODUCTION

A profiler, incorporating CTD and acoustic current meter technology, has been built for the Naval Ocean Research and Development Activity (NORDA) by Neil Brown Instrument Systems, Inc. The instrument is designed to gather data while being lowered from a slowly moving ship. It is intended for use in studies of oceanographic velocity and density features having vertical scales of ten centimeters or larger.

In a joint effort between NORDA and the NOAA Test and Evaluation Laboratory, the profiler was tested at the David Taylor Naval Ship Research and Development Center (DTNSRDC) in Carderock, Maryland. The results of those tests, which bear predominantly on the performance of the velocity sensors, are reported here, following a brief technical description of the instrument.

For a more general discussion of acoustic current meter technology, see reference 1.

2. INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION

Acoustic transducers for measuring current velocity components are contained in "fingers" attached to an assembly at the bottom of the pressure case. Side and frontal views of this assembly are seen in Figure 1, where the three acoustic paths, along which velocity components

are measured, are indicated by dashed lines between pairs of fingers. Two of the paths, those intersecting at right angles in the frontal view, lie in a plane which also contains the vertical axis of the instrument and so coalesce in the side view. The third path runs between two fingers one of which is longer than those defining the first two paths and the other of which is shorter. Hence, the resulting path is inclined at 45° with respect to the plane defined by the other two paths. These three paths thus measure current components in a skewed coordinate system. Each path is approximately 20 cm long.

Figure 1. Partial view of the instrument as seen from the side (on the left) and from the front (on the right) showing the arrangement of the velocity and CTD sensors as described in the text.

The instrument is intended for deployment in an over-the-side mode from a slowly moving ship, with a system for reducing the influence of ship motion on the instrument. As the ship moves, the instrument is oriented by a vane so that the

fingers are pointed in the upstream direction. Then as the apparatus is lowered slowly through the water, the flow induced by these two motions impinges upon it from forward and somewhat below the direction of the fingers, and passes nearly undisturbed across the three acoustic paths. Departures in direction from this mean flow of up to 50° in any direction by local velocity anomalies will likewise be sampled with little disturbance by the sensors or the other instrument components.

A standard set of CTD sensors, consisting of a conductivity cell and fast and slow response thermistors are mounted just downstream of the common point of intersection of the three acoustic paths. The position is given by the small square seen on the left side of Figure 1. All remaining sensors, consisting of a pressure transducer, a three-axis magnetometer and a three-axis accelerometer, are located in the pressure housing. All measured quantities are digitized, multiplexed, and transmitted in bit-serial fashion as an FSK code up a standard two-conductor CTD cable, which also provides power to the instrument. Principles underlying the velocity measuring technique have been reported in reference 2, although the associated electronic circuitry is different.

3. CALIBRATION TECHNIQUE

The output of the i -th acoustic path is denoted by q_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$. To be definite, the top three transducers in the frontal instrument view (Fig. 1) are numbered from one to three in order from left to right and each q_i is associated with the acoustic path which terminates at the correspondingly numbered transducer. Calibration then consisted of finding a functional form which approximated known current components in terms of the measured quantities q_i . The form which has been used is a power series

$$\hat{q}_i = \sum_j \sum_k \sum_l a_{ijkl} q_1^j q_2^k q_3^l \quad (1)$$

where the \hat{q}_i are the desired approximations to the known current components and the coefficients a_{ijkl} have been determined by least squares regression.

The results reported below are given in terms of a Cartesian coordinate system, fixed to the instrument and with current components denoted by u_i , where u_1 is positive in the direction of the fingers, u_3 is positive upward along the instrument axis, and u_2 is positive to the left of u_1 , forming a right-handed Cartesian system. A linear transformation α_{ij} can be found which takes the approximations q_i from the skewed to the Cartesian system, so that

$$\hat{u}_i = \sum_j \alpha_{ij} \hat{q}_j \quad (2)$$

Substitution of (1) into (2) yields the corresponding calibration formula for the Cartesian System, which has the form

$$\hat{u}_i = \sum_j \sum_k \sum_l b_{ijkl} q_1^j q_2^k q_3^l \quad (3)$$

In practice, (3) was used as a primary calibration formula, with the coefficients b found directly by least squares regression, thus providing calibration and orthogonalization in one step. Regressions up to third order were run, but terms higher than first order were found to be not significant, a fact consistent with the velocity sensors being linear and having a cosine response.

4. RESULTS IN STEADY FLOW

During these tests the instrument was mounted in a fixture which permitted it to be oriented by two independent rotations, one of which consisted of an azimuthal rotation about the instrument axis, measured positive in the clockwise sense as seen from above. The other rotation was in pitch about an axis normal to both the vertical and the direction of tow, with positive corresponding to clockwise rotation when the direction of tow was to the left. For both rotations, zero corresponded to the fingers being level and pointed in the direction of tow. By towing the instrument at known speeds and angles and recording the instrument output, the coefficients in (3) were determined. Differences between the values calculated from the resulting formula and those based on the known speeds and angles were then computed. The results shown below are representative of the differences found by using this procedure during some 250 runs and of the range of speeds and angles expected during field work.

Figure 2. Difference between measured and computed values of the u_1 velocity component at a tow speed of 40 cm/sec for various angles of azimuth and pitch, given as a percentage of tow speed.

The angular response of the instrument at constant tow speed is shown in Figure 2. The valley around zero azimuth and negative pitch, which also appears at other tow speeds, means that the u_1 velocity component measured by the instrument for that orientation is greater than that computed from the known tow speed and angles. The attitude of the instrument in that case is with the fingers in the same vertical plane as the direction of flow, but inclined downward toward the bottom of the tank. The anomaly can be traced entirely to the q_2 acoustic path and is attributed to disturbance of the flow by the CTD sensor package (see Fig. 1).

Figure 3. Difference between measured and computed values of u_3 velocity component, as a percent of tow speed, versus tow speed for zero pitch and azimuthal angles of $\pm 45^\circ$.

A complementary view, with fixed angles and various speeds, is given in Figure 3. All three components of speed have very low errors under these conditions, and the amount is comparable to those errors resulting from uncertainties in orientation of the instrument (about $\pm 0.5^\circ$).

Thus, the instrument has the two highly desirable characteristics of being linear and responding as the cosine of the angle between the flow and the acoustic path to within the limits of resolution available during the tests, except for the apparently avoidable CTD sensor interference.

5. RESULTS IN OSCILLATORY FLOW

The Vertical Planar Motion Mechanism³ attached to the carriage at DTNSRDC permits an instrument to be moved, without change of attitude, through a circular orbit in a vertical plane while simultaneously being transported down the tank at uniform mean speed by the tow carriage. The instrument was mounted in this mechanism with its axis vertical, was orbited at various angular speeds and radii, and was towed at various speeds, with the orbital plane making various angles θ with respect to the direction of tow.

A few of the 117 runs made in this "dynamic" mode are summarized in Figure 4. The RMS differences between measured and computed values, averaged over a few orbits, are given as a function of the ratio of tow speed to orbit speed, that is, the ratio of mean speed to oscillatory speed. This ratio controls the range of angles of the velocity with respect to the instrument. Only at ratios above 2 does the direction of the flow lie within

Figure 4. Root mean square difference between instantaneous values of measured and computed u_1 velocity components as a function of the ratio of tow speed to orbital speed of the instrument for the two indicated values of azimuth and zero pitch.

the range of angles illustrated in Figure 3, the normal operating range of the instrument.

A variety of errors can contribute to the results in Figure 4, including flexing of the instrument mount shaft and residual turbulence in the tank due to the vigorous stirring associated with these measurements, although quantitative estimates of these effects are not available. It is clear, however, that the anomaly in response evident in Figure 2 is not a significant effect here since it would appear only for the $\theta = 0$ case, whereas the observed RMS errors are independent of θ .

6. CONCLUSIONS

The acoustic phase-comparison technique used to measure currents follows linear and cosine response laws to within 1%, providing flow disturbances by surrounding objects are avoided. The errors reported here appear to be at the limit of present calibration accuracy. Acoustic current meters, which use the same measurement technique, are thus capable of a several-fold increase in accuracy if instrument self-wake interference can be eliminated.

7. REFERENCES

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